

Work Package 1 – Shared modelling framework and learnings

D1.2 – Description of scientific methods

Task 1.3 – Methods for Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Guide on the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) for bio-based products – Climate change

Lead Contractor: INSAT

Author(s): U. Javourez, D. Arbault, L. Hamelin (INSAT)

This document is a part of the ALIGNED project (grant no. 101059430) deliverable D1.2. It contains the practical approaches to harmonize and apply the latest recommendations on the climate change impacts' assessment phase of LCAs within the ALIGNED project.

PROJECTS DETAIL			
Project title	Aligning Life Cycle Assessment methods and bio-based sectors for improved environmental performance.		
Project acronym	ALIGNED	Start / Duration	10/2022 – 36 months
Type of Action		Website	www.alignedproject.eu

DELIVERABLE DETAILS			
Dissemination level	Public	Nature	Report
Due date (M)	M18 (March/2024)	Submission date	31/03/2024

DELIVERABLE CONTRIBUTORS			
	Name	Organisation	Job title
Deliverable leader	Lorie Hamelin	INSAT	Professor
Contributing Author(s)	Ugo Javourez	INSAT	Post-doctoral Researcher
	Damien Arbault	INSAT	Post-doctoral Researcher
	Lorie Hamelin	INSAT	Professor

Reviewer(s)	Kira Lancz	AAU	Research Assistant
	Massimo Pizzol	AAU	Professor
	Agneta Ghose	AAU	Assistant Professor
	Damien Arbault	INSAT	Post-doctoral Researcher
	Marcos Watanabe	NTNU	
Final review and quality approval	Massimo Pizzol	AAU	Professor

DOCUMENT HISTORY			
Date	Version	Name	Changes
02/02/2024	v0.1	Guide on the Life Cycle Im Assessment (LCIA) for based products - Clir change	First draft
18/02/2024	v0.2	Guide on the Life Cycle Im Assessment (LCIA) for based products - Clir change	Considering comments
19/03/2024	v1.0	Guide on the Life Cycle Im Assessment (LCIA) for based products - Clir change	Final
20/09/2025	v2.0	Guide on the Life Cycle Im Assessment (LCIA) for based products - Clir change	Revised version

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS.....	6
1. INTRODUCTION ON LCIA OF BIO-BASED PRODUCTS.....	7
1.1. LCIA HARMONIZATION IS MUCH NEEDED.....	7
1.2. THE ROLE OF LCIA METHODS.....	7
2. CHALLENGES IN HARMONISING CLIMATE CHANGE LCIA METHODS FOR BIO-BASED PRODUCTS.....	9
3. RELEVANCE OF BIOGENIC CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS INDICATORS.....	11
4. DIFFERENT METRICS QUANTIFYING CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS.....	12
4.1. WARMING POTENTIAL INDICATORS.....	12
4.1.1. <i>Global Warming Potential (GWP)</i>	12
4.1.2. <i>Global Warming Potential “star” (GWP*)</i>	13
4.1.3. <i>Global Warming potential “bio” (GWPbio)</i>	13
4.2. TEMPERATURE-RELATED INDICATORS.....	14
4.2.1. <i>Global temperature change potential (GTP)</i>	14
4.2.2. <i>Global mean temperature change (GMTC)</i>	14
4.3. CURRENT RECOMMENDATIONS OF CLIMATE CHANGE METRICS IN LCA STUDIES.....	15
5. ON INTEGRATING THE DYNAMIC ASPECT OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN LCA.....	15
5.1. PERIOD-SPECIFIC GWP CF.....	16
5.1.1. <i>Levasseur method</i>	16
5.1.2. <i>Ventura method</i>	16
5.2. PERIOD-SPECIFIC GTP CF.....	17
5.3. BEYOND CHARACTERIZATION FACTORS, TOWARDS COMPLIANCE WITH CLIMATE TARGETS.....	17
6. ON THE ACCOUNTING OF BIOGENIC VERSUS FOSSIL CARBON FLOWS IN LCAS (ISSUE 4) 18	
6.1. ON THE 0/0 APPROACH.....	19
6.2. ON THE -1/+1 APPROACH.....	19
6.3. ON THE OTHER APPROACHES TO ACCOUNT FOR BIOGENIC CARBON FLOWS.....	20
6.4. ALIGNMENT OF STANDARDS AND PRACTICES.....	22
7. TOWARDS CONSISTENT ESTIMATION OF CLIMATE IMPACTS IN LCAS OF BIO-BASED PRODUCTS.....	23
7.1. BASELINE ALIGNED RECOMMENDATIONS.....	23
7.2. INTEGRATING TIME EFFECTS IN CLIMATE SCORES COMPUTATION IN PRACTICE.....	25
8. CONCLUSION.....	27
9. REFERENCES.....	28

List of figures

Figure 1 – Substance to damage modelling in LCIA frameworks..... 8
Figure 2 – Terminology for system boundaries to develop LCA for a bio-based sector.....21
Figure 3– ALIGNED recommendations for estimating climate impacts of biobased production – synthesis.23

List of tables

Table 1 ALIGNED Tiered approach for including time effects in climate change scores computation
.....26

Executive summary

This document presents practical approaches to harmonize and apply the latest recommendations on the impacts' assessment phase of LCAs within the ALIGNED project. **It specifically addresses the climate change impact category**, of foremost importance for bio-based production. A synthesis of the latest research and existing climate change assessment frameworks tailored to LCA are provided. As for each component of ALIGNED's methodological framework, a guidance formulated as a tiered approach is proposed. The guidance covers the strategies to adopt to include time-explicit Greenhouse gas (GHG) flows accounting in the LCIA phase and discusses the need to discern distinguish biogenic from fossil carbon when assessing climate change in LCAs. Time-specific characterization factors (CF) for Global Warming Potential (GWP) and integrated Global Temperature Potential (iGTP) for different time horizons are suggested from recent literature, compared and their implications discussed. Their usability in real case LCAs and availability within existing LCA software are improved with import routines and calculation tools accessible in the project repository.

Acronyms and abbreviations

ABBREVIATIONS	Description
(A)GTP	(Absolute) Global Temperature change Potential
(A)GWP	(Absolute) Global Warming Potential
CF	Characterization factors
DAC	Direct air capture
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GMTC	Global mean temperature change
iGTP	integrated GTP
KPI	Key performance indicator
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impacts assessment

1. Introduction on LCIA of bio-based products

1.1. LCIA Harmonization is much needed

Assessing the environmental performance of the bio-based sectors requires consistent and comparable quantification and accounting methodologies. To evaluate impacts on a full system perspective, life cycle analysis (LCA) has emerged as the leading tool to support decision making and guide transition towards sustainable economies. Although the key principles of LCA are formalized into ISO standards 14040-46 (ISO, 2006), these still provide relative flexibility in interpretation. Therefore, a variety of LCA-based assessment frameworks are available, similar but different methodologies and results.

For example, the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) established and used by the European Commission to compare products demonstrated lack of comparability between different sectors and was found incompatible with the Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) system (Durão et al., 2020). Regarding bio-based sectors, LCA studies on individual products present a large variability (Zuiderveen et al., 2023), leading to confusing decision supports and ultimately slowing the pace of environmental improvement. Hence, the four stages of the LCA method (as defined by ISO standards) require harmonization and scientific improvements (Pawelzik et al., 2013), namely: Goal and scope, Life cycle inventory (LCI), Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) and Interpretation.

1.2. The role of LCIA methods

The present Task 1.3 specifically deals with the challenges associated with the LCIA phase in assessing the potential environmental impacts of bio-based products. LCIA aims to translate the flows of emissions from and to the environment, as identified during the LCI analysis, into potential environmental impacts. To this end, developers of LCIA methods compute characterization factors (CF) from latest scientific knowledge to capture the effects of the unitary emission of a given substance on a given impact category (and a given environmental compartment, if required; see **Figure 1**). As for any models, deriving CFs implies simplifying complex environmental mechanisms into single values, simplification coming with their own sets of assumptions and normative choices (Negishi et al., 2018). Efforts have been made in the last decade to build coherent sets of LCIA methods integrating latest improvements in corresponding science fields (e.g. climate science for the climate change impact category), integrating novel impacts pathways in existing LCIA methods in a consistent way, increasing their usability within existing LCA software readily available (such as Simapro, for example), and moving towards a spatially- and time-explicit LCIA resolution. While harmonization is ongoing, some methodological and conceptual differences remain between the most advanced available LCIA methods, such as LC-IMPACT, IMPACT WORLD +, or ReCiPe. These include the characterization models used, the kind of effects (aspects, diseases, ecosystems) covered, the fate, exposure and effects modelling (e.g. marginal or average impacts), the time horizon proposed, the emission compartments available, the level of spatial differentiation and geographical validity, among others (Rosenbaum, 2018).

In short, once available in an LCA software, a given LCIA method provides a set of CFs which allows to quantify the potential environmental effects of the LCI data associated with the system under study, at different intermediary impact categories (midpoints, endpoints), up to the areas of protection (**Figure 1**), by simply multiplying all the emissions with their corresponding CFs.

Figure 1 – Substance to damage modelling in LCIA frameworks

2. Challenges in harmonising climate change LCIA methods for bio-based products

Apart from the system-wise need for LCIA harmonization, key LCIA methodological choices arise when it comes to bio-based production. One of the main incentives to shift towards bio-based production is to reduce the use of fossil resources (Pawelzik et al., 2013), which is mostly motivated by its consequences on the climate change impact category, itself identified as the highest contributors (i.e. largest threat) to potential damages on human health and ecosystems areas of protections (Verones et al., 2020). **This guide specifically addresses** the challenges to fairly and consistently - that is, across systems and sectors - comparing bio-based and fossil-based products for **the climate change impact category** itself. Indeed, it requires a harmonized strategy to account for biogenic and fossil carbon flows as a function of system and time boundaries, but also adequate and easily accessible tools to operationally consider the time dimension in the LCIA phase. Guidance is further required to know when increased modeling effort really yields value-added information used in the process of decision-making, and what are the most adequate metrics in each context (Brandão et al., 2024).

Biomass (what is further referred to as biogenic) carbon flows used to not be systematically reported in LCA studies, due to a body of literature suggesting that short capture/release cycles of biogenic carbon in bio-based products were negligible in the calculation of climate change impact category indicators (Andersen et al., 2021). This is referred to as the “carbon neutrality” hypothesis of biomass and related bio-based products. In consequence, static LCA approaches without the accounting of biogenic CO₂ was often deemed sufficient to estimate the potential climate change impacts of products and services, including bio-based ones. “Static” LCA refers to discarding the time dimensions of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with the life cycle of a product or service (during the LCI phase), and to disregard the influence of time in the LCIA phase, more specifically the influence of the timing of GHG emissions on climate change impacts. Yet, increased evidence suggests that the “carbon neutrality” hypothesis is not suitable to assess the climate change impacts of bio-based sectors, as summarized by the statement “carbon neutrality does not imply climate neutrality” (Andersen et al., 2021; Cucurachi et al., 2022). This is because the severity of climate change is related to the maximum temperature or GHG concentration in the atmosphere, the time to peak, among other indicators (Cherubini et al., 2011; Tiruta-Barna, 2021). In short, **climate change impacts calculations are intrinsically linked with the temporal distribution of GHGs flows** (Tiruta-Barna, 2021), effects only neglectable in specific situations.

One key feature of the GHG emissions profile of bio-based production is the time separation between the capture and release of biogenic carbon embedded in products (Pawelzik et al., 2013). Numerous factors influence this GHG profile (magnitude, time-distribution, etc.), such as growth characteristics of selected biomass feedstocks, land management practices, lifetime of the bio-product in the Technosphere, to mention a few (Seigné-Itoiz et al., 2021). For example, some bio-based chemicals (e.g. glycerol) might present lifetime from a few weeks to several years before being emitted back as part of their end-of-life, while construction materials might mobilize carbon for several decades, up

to centuries if considering the potential multiple recycling loops. The overall climate benefits of temporary carbon storage are not only contrasted -pros and cons synthesized in (Brandão et al., 2024)-, but also scope- and system-specific. **Four challenges** have been raised in the context of the ALIGNED project when it comes to assessing the climate change impacts of bio-based products.

Challenge 1: Should one assess “total” climate change only, or is it necessary to also (or instead) separately assess the impacts of climate change due to biogenic carbon flows and fossil carbon flows? If so, under which situation should such a distinction be made?

Challenge 2: Several metrics exist or are emerging to estimate the climate change impact category (e.g. GWP, GTP, GMTC). Which one should be discussed as a priority? How does this indicator choice influence the interpretation of the results?

Challenge 3: How to get and compute time-explicit inventory data and characterization factors for selected climate change impact metrics? When is this relevant?

Challenge 4: How to select the way biogenic carbon flows is included in climate change impact scores, so that it is coherent, fair and consistent? (0/0, -1/+1 approach, etc.)

These challenges were used to structure **sections 3-6**. As these are interrelated, ALIGNED proposed a single harmonized set of recommendations for all the challenges in **section 7**.

3. On the relevance of discerning biogenic and fossil carbon flows in LCIs

This section relates to **Challenge 1**: *Should one assess “total” climate change only, or is it necessary to also (or instead) separately assess the climate change impacts due to biogenic carbon flows and fossil carbon flows? If so, under which situation should such a distinction be made?*

Needless to remind that the atmosphere makes no difference between carbon flows, either fossil or biogenic (Cucurachi et al., 2022). This is the main reason why ALIGNED advocates that at least the interpretation of climate change scores should include an impact category integrating both, referred to as the “total” climate change impacts score. Yet, at stake for LCA is how the results will be used. **In other words, is distinguishing the contribution to climate change scores of biogenic carbon flows from fossil flows useful for decision making?** Albeit available LCA studies scarcely report both, their distinction can provide additional insights if one wishes to monitor the substitution rate or magnitude of fossil carbon by biogenic carbon, or to reflect biogenic carbon sequestration as well as carbon stocks maintenance and changes. Performing this distinction in practice when elaborating the LCI of specific case studies does not induce extra work, but neither does it free practitioners from other normative choices. For example, implementing direct air capture (DAC) technologies to reuse or store carbon is acting, biophysically speaking, as a biomass-based system. Depending on the carbon flow labelling (e.g. fossil, non-fossil, biogenic, from/to soil or biomass stock, etc.) available in the LCA software and LCIA method being used, different DAC carbon flows labelling could be applied in practice, with different implications on the interpretation of the “biogenic” climate change impacts.

In summary, **ALIGNED suggests always including the total climate change impact category**, aggregating the effects of both fossil and biogenic carbon flows. Yet, depending on the KPI deemed relevant for the decision to support by the LCA study, this “total” indicator could be amended with a subdivision of the climate change impacts due to biogenic carbon flows only and fossil carbon flows only, with their respective contribution to total impacts interpreted and discussed. This would require using an LCIA method where all three climate change indicators are available, for example the Environmental Footprint (EF) or IPCC 2021. Importantly, **this recommendation is valid for cradle-to-grave LCA studies where the entire life cycle is considered**, from carbon uptake during biomass growth to carbon released during the end-of-life of bio-based products. For partial, truncated, cradle-to-gate studies, specific adjustments to this recommendation are necessary (cf. **section 7**).

4. Different metrics quantifying climate change impacts

This section relates to **Challenge 2**: *Several metrics exist or are emerging to estimate the climate change impact category (e.g. GWP, GTP, GMTC). Which one should be discussed as a priority? How does this indicator choice influence the interpretation of the results?*

Climate change impacts metrics are the basis on which the potential impacts on climate change due to the products or services assessed can be compared across alternatives and studies. A first reason to monitor climate change is because this is a key threat to the areas of protection (e.g. human health and ecosystems quality; Figure 1). Yet, its peculiar status in global public debate makes it an unavoidable KPI to include in LCA studies, as a mid-point indicator. As an impact category, climate change is measured as the modification of global warming triggered by a modification of climate drivers (among which global GHG emissions). The scientific basis of the cause effect chain and modeling of climate change impacts as a function of GHG emission profiles – among the other climate drivers – and carbon pools are documented and continuously updated by the IPCC, along with the definition of intermediate metrics (Calvin et al., 2023). IPCC also proposes metrics to estimate the contribution to climate change of unit pulse of emissions, therefore suited for LCA applications as these usually assess small systems compared to global climate drivers. GHG pulse emissions first lead to a change in radiative forcing, further leading to a change in global mean temperature with a lag and magnitude depending on the GHG (its radiative efficiency, atmospheric lifetime, among others; Olivié and Peters, 2013). To compare the climate effects of different GHGs, comparing their impact potential to that of CO₂ has been the norm, albeit this choice is increasingly discussed (Tirutu-Barna, 2021). A non-exhaustive list of the main climate change impacts indicators usually available in LCIA methods are further briefly described. Readers can also refer to the recent overview and ranking of climate change midpoint metrics proposed by (Brandão et al., 2024).

4.1. Warming potential indicators

4.1.1. Global Warming Potential (GWP)

Global warming potential (GWP) is the most used climate change midpoint indicator, as promoted in multiple IPCC assessment reports and integrated in most available LCIA methods. It calculates the relative radiative forcing of a GHG over a given time horizon, as compared to a reference substance (CO₂). While the radiative efficiency measures the ability of a GHG to trap energy, radiative forcing measures the change in net radiative flux (W.m⁻²) induced by the change in climate drivers, including GHGs concentrations time profiles. Pulse emissions are usually computed through simple decay function, except for CO₂. Estimating the decay function of CO₂ in the atmosphere requires considering the interactions between the carbon pools (including oceans among others), usually estimated through the Bern carbon cycle. As such, GWP is a unit-less relative measure, but can also be expressed in absolute values (referred to as AGWP, expressed in W.m⁻².yr.kg⁻¹). In practice, GWP provides a large flexibility in its implementation. GWP values can greatly vary depending on normative choices such as the definition of the time horizon of the emission profiles (Calvin et al., 2023). The latter needs to be fixed in GWP calculation: the choice of a time horizon directly relates whether the final user of the assessment (here, the LCA) wishes to emphasize shorter-term effects (e.g. rate of temperature rise) or longer-term (e.g. sea level rise) linked to the alteration of the “thermal budget”

induced by the product or service under study. A 100-year time horizon has been suggested by IPCC, leading to the definition of a GWP100 metric, which is rather a short-term perspective considering the long lifetime of CO₂. It is the most widely used indicator and is integrated in almost all available LCIA methods. Naturally, the main critic about the GWP indicator lies in the arbitrary definition of the time horizon rather based on cultural values (e.g. intergenerational equity) than scientifically justified (Beloin-Saint-Pierre et al., 2020). The choice of time horizon can modify the climate scores of a product system by more than one order of magnitude depending on the GHG emissions profile and the presence of short-life GHGs (see below; Cain et al., 2019). Only the IPCC, 2021 LCIA method proposes other GWP indicators than GWP100, such as GWP20 and GWP500. The rest of the LCIA methods currently available in LCA software generally only consider GWP100 (e.g. the EF LCIA method) or use other climate change midpoint metrics (e.g. IMPACT World +; see below) or alternatively only provides endpoint assessments (e.g. LC-IMPACTS). Some alternative GWP definitions exist, further summarized.

4.1.2. Global Warming Potential “star” (GWP*)

GWP*, pronounced “GWP star”, is presented as an updated version of GWP in which the atmospheric lifetimes of GHGs are considered. This is because the different lifetimes of GHGs in the atmosphere lead to different warming effects. For example, methane atmospheric lifetime is around 12 years in comparison to carbon dioxide which can be thousands of years (Inman, 2008). GWP* is also expressed in CO₂-warming-equivalent (kg CO₂-eq) and is estimated based on a model. This builds on the fact that sustaining a change in the rate of emissions of short-life GHGs provides similar effects on global mean temperatures as a pulse capture or release of CO₂ (Smith et al., 2021). Albeit recognized as a more scientifically accurate way to quantify the warming equivalent of GHG emissions (Cain et al., 2019), it is currently not recommended by IPCC (IPCC, 2021). This is because the internationally agreed “net zero GHG emissions” target was established using the GWP metric, implying that global temperature peaks and declines after the target is met. In contrast, in terms of GWP*, “net zero GHG emissions” implies temperature stabilization, not declination (IPCC, 2021). Therefore, using GWP* would encourage policies underestimating the consequences of future high temperatures in favor of short-term positive effects (Meinshausen and Nicholls, 2022). Yet GWP* promoters claim that this metric allows both short- and long-life GHGs to keep being included together in carbon budgets, leading to more efficient policies aligned with long term temperature goals (Cain et al., 2019). As for conventional GWP, GWP* remains a simple metric relying on linearities assumptions which de facto does not capture the complexity of the climate system (Lynch et al., 2020).

4.1.3. Global Warming potential “bio” (GWPbio)

GWPbio is a CO₂-focused indicator initially derived to estimate the potential climate impacts of bioenergy in a context where it was generally acknowledged that the use of biomass was carbon neutral (Cherubini et al., 2011). It was specifically built to compute the fact that the time delay between sequences of biogenic carbon cycles (e.g. deforestation for bioenergy followed by reforestation) had significant consequences on climate change. In other words, CO₂ emissions from biomass combustion remain for a while in the atmospheric pool before being totally reabsorbed by ecosystems. A solution to capture this effect is to compute GWP indices for biogenic CO₂ as a function of the rotation period of harvested biomass: the GWPbio (Cherubini et al., 2011). This approach does not require the estimation of temporally explicit LCI, only to identify the typical rotation period. The GWPbio is then calculated by applying the corresponding GWPbio CO₂ CF (between 0 and 1 depending on the rotation period) to the total biogenic carbon flow as identified during the LCI phase (Breton et al., 2018). GWPbio method has been refined since its first formulation to include effects of

e.g. albedo and has been applied to several case studies comparing biofuels against fossil fuels (Breton et al., 2018). However, IPCC still considers this method lacks robustness and applicability (Calvin et al., 2023). Notably, using GWP_{bio} is equivalent to applying a time weighting factor for biogenic CO₂, while the time dimension of the rest of carbon (and other) flows would remain neglected, leading to potential temporal inconsistencies (Breton et al., 2018). Moreover, the way GWP_{bio} considers that biogenic carbon emitted as CO₂ (e.g. biomass combustion) will be sequestrated back can be regarded as ambiguous or arbitrary, as there is no way to ensure to which extent the reforested area will behave in practice, and really capture as much carbon back as assumed in the GWP_{bio} model (Ventura, 2022).

4.2. Temperature-related indicators

4.2.1. Global temperature change potential (GTP)

The use of global temperature change potential (GTP) as a midpoint indicator goes one step further in the cause effect chain of climate system modelling. While GWP translates GHG pulses into radiative forcing, GTP translates GHG pulses directly into the potentially triggered response of temperature to a given time horizon (Breton et al., 2018). GTP can be expressed absolutely (AGTP, in Kelvin), or relatively to a reference substance (usually in kg CO₂-eq). Albeit scientifically recognized as more consistent to reflect the actual consequences of GHG emissions on temperature change, the same drawbacks as GWP also apply to GTP (Tirutu-Barna, 2021). These drawbacks are reinforced by the fact that calculating GTP requires a more complex climate model as compared to GWP, leading to the need of more assumptions, calibration, and likely more uncertainties (Oliví and Peters, 2013). For example, methods to estimate the changes in radiative forcing related to a pulse of GHG emissions are more robust than those directly estimating changes in global temperature from pulse emissions. Yet, GTP estimations from long-life GHGs emissions pulses (e.g. CO₂) have been found relatively accurate (Shine et al., 2005). To adapt the GTP metric to fairly account for the effects of short life GHGs (e.g. CH₄), a combined temperature change potential (CGTP) metric has been defined. Somehow, CGTP was designed to ‘correct’ GTP the same way GWP* was designed to ‘correct’ GWP. Again, computing the GTP metric requires defining a time horizon. In practice, GTP₄₀ or GTP₅₀ are estimated to give similar numerical results as GWP₁₀₀: they capture short term effects. GTP₁₀₀ is available in the Impact World + LCIA method to represents long terms climate impacts at the midpoint level (Bulle et al., 2019). Instead of this relative short versus long term separation, some practitioners advocate for the definition of absolute (calendar) time horizons which would be aligned with climate targets such as 2100 (Tirutu-Barna, 2021). A stepwise calculation procedure for absolute GTP is available in e.g. Iordan et al., (2023).

4.2.2. Global mean temperature change (GMTC)

Global mean temperature change (GMTC) estimates how the temperature is modified at the global scale, over a time profile, because of a given GHG emissions time profile. While GTP is a relative metric (normalized to CO₂) estimating the effects of temperature changes at the end of the time horizon (a point-value), GMTC provides a time-dependent absolute global temperature change (a profile) as a function of a GHG emissions profile linked to the life cycle of the product or system under study. This temperature profile can further be integrated (referred to as the iGMTC), but in this case becomes a warming indicator (Tirutu-Barna, 2021). The main reason to adopt GMTC-related metrics in LCA is to provide decision-makers with indicators aligned with international targets to mitigate climate change, expressed in climate targets or thresholds for temperature (e.g. the 1.5°C target of Paris agreements). Moreover, GMTC metrics allow to monitor key yet differentiated impacts of climate changes (such as magnitude of peaks, time to climate neutrality, etc.) which are absent in integrated and normalized metrics such as GWP. As a temporally explicit indicator, computing GMTC requires

temporally-explicit LCI flows. In turn, GMTC is only applicable in dynamic LCAs (e.g. Shen et al., 2022), hence not available in conventional LCA software (**section 5**).

4.3. Current recommendations of climate change metrics in LCA studies

The need to provide sets of indicators to capture the diversity of climate change-related impacts at the midpoint level, instead of providing one aggregated value, is not new. Importantly, the latest IPCC AR6 does not recommend any specific metric as the selection depends on which aspects of climate change are seen as the most important to a situation, a stakeholder, and over which time horizon (IPCC, 2021). The UNEP/SETAC recommends at least capturing short-term and long-term effects, for example by selecting GWP100 and GTP100 indicators at the midpoint level, as in the IMPACT World + LCIA method (Bulle et al., 2019). ALIGNED recommendations were formulated in **section 7**.

5. On integrating the time dimension of climate change in LCA

This section relates to **Challenge 3**: *How to get and compute time-explicit inventory data and characterization factors for selected climate change impact metrics? When is this relevant?*

To increase the accuracy and scientific ground on which climate change impact scores of bio-based products are calculated and interpreted in LCA studies, shifting towards time dependent characterization factors (CF) has increasingly been put forward. The timing of emissions determines the magnitude, duration and profile of the response of global temperatures to emissions changes, as described in **section 4**. When specifically dealing with bio-based products, their carbon storage effects are disregarded in static LCAs, regardless of the chosen indicator (Cucurachi et al., 2022). Considering the products' lifecycle temporality implies adding the time dimension to both flow inventories and CFs. Therefore, attempts to include this time effect exogenously in the CF (e.g. GWP_{bio} , **section 4.1.3**) does not seem fully adequate for the broader bio-based sectors LCAs. Finally, effects of land use change, the change in global carbon storage in terrestrial pools, recognized as strongly correlated with the bio-based sectors, are also intrinsically linked to a time dimension (Schmidt et al., 2015).

Including the timing effects of GHG emissions can in practice be integrated into all metrics presented in the previous **section 4**. The simplest approach consists in defining a vector of CFs over the selected time horizon (usually on a yearly basis), instead of providing a single value. It is equivalent in defining one aggregated pulse emission per year and per GHG, instead of one aggregated GHG pulse emissions over the entire time horizon. These are further referred to as "time-explicit CFs". **Implementing time-explicit CFs requires, as a first step, to have expressed the LCI with the same temporal step.** Time-explicit CFs are usually available on a yearly basis, meaning that the LCI of studied systems should also be established on a yearly basis. Other impact categories than climate change might also be affected by time dependencies of emission. For example, for toxicity-related impacts, the fate factors representing the distribution and transformation of chemicals in the environment are

also time-dependent (Shimako et al., 2018). Yet, methods to calculate the dynamic effects of these impacts are still under development (Beloin-Saint-Pierre et al., 2020) and not further presented herein. Albeit a dynamic LCA can take various hybrid form (Breton et al., 2018), here it is referred to LCA studies explicitly implementing a time dimension to both the LCI and LCIA stages (Beloin-Saint-Pierre et al., 2020). Hereafter, only the climate change impact category is covered at the midpoint level, and the main approaches to derive time-explicit CF tailored for LCA applications are summarized (non-exhaustive list).

5.1. Time-explicit GWP CF

As a short theoretical background, radiative forcing and carbon dioxide cycle modeling needs to be defined. The radiative forcing is usually simplified as the radiative efficiency per the concentration of the GHG in the atmosphere but can also be expressed per kg of specific GHG emitted. All the shortcomings related to the interpretation of GWP mentioned in the last section also apply here.

5.1.1. Levasseur method

The reference method to derive time-explicit CFs for GWP in LCA studies was proposed by Levasseur et al., (2010). These are calculated as the total radiative forcing generated per time unit (generally a year). Here, the main difference with the static GWP approach lies in the fact that GWP_t (at year t) does consider all the GHG flows (linked to the LCI of the studied system) which occurred from the time of emission and until year t , hence considering the cumulative effects of emissions. In other words, while the static GWP is simply the net amount of emissions for each GHG_i (aggregated over the whole life cycle) multiplied by a single CF_i (e.g. 1 kg CO₂-eq.kg⁻¹ for i being carbon dioxide), estimating the instantaneous GWP_t (at year t) requires to sum the effects of all emissions up to that year considering their decay functions. Once calculated for each year of the selected time horizon, the total “dynamic” GWP can be defined as the cumulative sum of all the GWP_t over the time horizon (Pawelzik et al., 2013). This is in essence similar to the approach developed by Schmidt et al., (2015), who proposed to modify the definition of the static GWP method to include the positive effects of delaying GHG emissions, in a context where estimating indirect land use change impacts in LCA was still missing. As for its static version, the time horizon appears as a cut-off threshold in GWP estimation. As defined, the closer t to the time horizon, the lower CF_t . This is because the radiative forcing associated with the pulse emissions of each year t are smaller the closer the pulse emission is to the time horizon, meaning their contribution to GWP decreases the further in the future the emissions are generated. It means that for a time horizon of 100 years, an emission occurring at year 100 (or after) would have no influence on GWP_{100} , hence reflecting the benefit of postponing emissions. Needless to add that as long as the time horizon is finite, there is implicitly a discounting (Beloin-Saint-Pierre et al., 2020).

5.1.2. Ventura method

Ventura, (2022) advocates that the practice of late (relative to the time horizon) emissions “discounting” is not aligned with LCA principles. The main arguments are summarized as follows: all LCI flows should be assessed in the LCIA phase, and the same time horizon to characterize (here meaning: quantifying the potential impacts of) each substance flows should be considered regardless of their timing related to time horizon. Ventura, (2022) demonstrates that the Levasseur method does not comply with these requirements and proposes a modification of the calculation formula.

Notably, Ventura, (2022) highlights the ambiguity of the time horizon. Time horizon was initially defined as the temporal period over which the potential impacts linked to an emission are assessed but is in practice considered equivalent to what the author refers to as the “total observation duration”. In other words, in LCA studies, Ventura, (2022) considers that the impacts of all LCI emissions should be calculated with the time horizon, meaning that even the latest emission in the temporally explicit LCI (called life cycle duration) should be assessed with the same time horizon. It means that the total observable duration equals time horizon plus life cycle duration. The approach of Ventura, (2022) still relies on a choice of a time horizon, a value linked with the cultural perspective on intergenerational equity (Beloin-Saint-Pierre et al., 2020), and still accounts for the benefits of delaying emissions, but without overestimating these by neglecting all emissions occurring after 100 years like in GWP100. Following the terminology of (Brandão et al., 2024), this is equivalent in implementing a “sliding” temporal window for GWP calculation instead of the “truncated” one implemented in (Levasseur et al., 2010). The proposed adapted GWP by Ventura, (2022) is however not available in LCA software.

5.2. Using AGTP functions to compute temperature-change based metrics

As pointed out by LCA specialists (Frischknecht et al., 2016), ‘cumulative metrics like GWP or iGTP can ensure consistency across impact categories, while GTP is a special case as it is an instantaneous indicator’. As a result, using GTP metric with a constant Time Horizon for GHG flows corresponding to different points in time would lead to inconsistent results. Calculating temperature-related indicators in time-explicit LCIA requires a specific framework, in which the temperature change from a pulse emission can be assessed for any point in future time. In other words, temperature-based indicators should be calculated using AGTP functions: $AGTP_X(t_0, t)$ maps the effects on temperature change (in °C) at year $t > t_0$, from a pulse of GHG substance X emitted at year t_0 .

The ALIGNED tool allows a simplified computation of GMTC and iGMTC over time, generated by a time-distributed GHG inventory. This tool is based on a model developed by Shimako et al (2016a) and further made available online at <https://www.insa-toulouse.fr/cci-tool/> (an offline version can also be downloaded). The user will find in the ALIGNED repository, along with the present document: a spreadsheet calculator (ALIGNED-T1.3-CC calculator.xlsx) with a tutorial to use it (ALIGNED-T1.3-Tutorial-CC) and an appendix to describe its mathematical model (ALIGNED-T1.3-Appendix_Tier3).

5.3. Beyond characterization factors, towards compliance with climate targets

Moving climate change midpoint indicators towards time-explicit and temperature-based metrics would enable benchmarking the climate effects of the system under study against global climate targets. In practice, this would require moving beyond the use of CFs, hence outside of the conventional matrix-based LCA calculation framework implemented in available LCA software, to compute the nonlinear climate phenomenon. The [climate change impact tool](#) made by INSAT is ready to use and transparently documented in peer reviewed literature (Shimako et al., 2016b; Tiruta-Barna, 2021). It provides the temporal evolution of several indicators of warming effects

(instantaneous and cumulative) as well as the absolute global mean temperature change indicator (instantaneous and cumulative) as a function of a time distribution of GHG emissions for all GHG substances available in the biosphere database available in conventional LCA software. Among the benefits, deriving such indicators for climate change attenuates the influence of the choice of a time horizon on the interpretation of the results and allows to capture a broader perspective of potential climate impacts (future temperatures, rate of warming, cumulative warming) while remaining at the midpoint level. Finally, it unlocks direct comparison with science-based time targets (e.g. time to peak, time to climate neutrality, etc.). Yet, difficulties remain when it comes to taking decisions based on multiple indicators formulated as time profiles. To this end, attempts have been made to aggregate the multidimensional features of climate impacts into a single score. This is the case of the Climate change Impact Potential indicator (Brandão et al., 2024), which integrates impacts related to future temperatures (e.g. heatwaves), to the rate of warming (e.g. capacity for adaptation), and to the cumulative warming (e.g. sea-level rise). Yet, as for any aggregated metrics, the different aspects have been weighted, adding an additional layer of value choices when interpreting the results. The tiered recommendations of ALIGNED related to the integration of dynamic aspects in the LCA of bio-based production are formulated in **section 7**.

6. On the accounting of biogenic carbon flows in LCAs (issue 4)

This section relates to **Challenge 4**: *How to select the way biogenic carbon flows is included in climate change impact scores, so that it is coherent, fair and consistent? (0/0, -1/+1 approach, etc.)*

Consistent accounting of carbon flows in LCAs is key to ensure the consistency and reproducibility of the impact scores, particularly for climate change. Yet, different LCA standards and guidelines use different normative choices to assess biogenic and fossil carbon flows in the LCIA phase. This is important as differentiating the methods to account for biogenic carbon against fossil carbon will lead to various LCA scores and environmental statements for the product under study. This accounting issue primarily relates to the characterization factor (CF) of CO₂ in normalized and relative midpoint metrics (that is GWP and GTP, see **section 4**), and more specifically to their application in “static” LCAs.

In the approach called ‘-1/+1’ (Cucurachi et al., 2022), the GWP or GTP associated with the emission of 1 kg of CO₂ – regardless of being biogenic or fossil – is defined as 1 kg CO₂-eq. In other words, the GWP characterization factor of the emitted CO₂ is +1. Removing CO₂ from the atmosphere, for example by increasing biogenic carbon stocks through biomass growth, can therefore be regarded as ‘negative emissions’ and be accounted for with a GWP characterization factor of -1 kg CO₂-eq¹.

¹ Strictly speaking, the resource ‘CO₂ in air’ is consumed during the plant growth. So, as any other resource, it is counted with a positive value in main LCI databases like ecoinvent. Therefore, it is artificially assigned a negative CF.

The '0/0' approach is also often used to account for biogenic carbon flows. The rationale is that, in the long-term, biogenic carbon release and capture are balanced, so their monitoring is not necessary (see also GWP_{bio} , **section 4.1.3**). In practice, both approaches are recognized as valid by different standards, albeit under specific conditions (Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2023). Selected approaches notably require aligning with the selected system boundaries of the LCA study, as further detailed. Other hybrid approaches exist such as the -1/0 approach (Cucurachi et al., 2022) and the -1/+1* approach (Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2023). Regardless of the approach taken for biogenic carbon flows accounting, fossil carbon dioxide flows are always characterized with a GWP or GTP CF of 1 kg CO₂-eq.

6.1. On the 0/0 approach

This approach consists in characterizing the aggregated CO₂ LCI flows both from and to the biosphere with a GWP or GTP characterization factor of 0. Among the advantages, the ease of implementation is put forward. Indeed, precisely quantifying the biogenic carbon mass balances becomes irrelevant to calculate climate impacts. In turn, this provides flexibility to the practitioner who can prioritize modeling efforts to the biogenic processes deemed important, and for which robust and unambiguous methods exist, but at a cost of increased subjectivity and potential incompleteness. This approach has unsurprisingly been widely implemented in LCA studies. Although the main LCIA methods available do propose the -1/1 approach as default, in practice a 0/0 approach can be implemented by either modifying the default values to 0/0, or simply by not accounting for any biogenic CO₂ flows in the LCI phase. This approach is now increasingly criticized and challenged, the main arguments are summarized below.

First, from a theoretical standpoint, the net 0 biogenic carbon approximation would only be valid if all the carbon pools absorption abilities remain the same perpetually, following critics to the GWP_{bio} approach (**section 4.1.3**). This is not what is observed in practice. For instance, the ocean carbon sink is less efficient with higher water temperatures among others (feedback loop of the climate change effects; Calvin et al., 2023). The same happens with global changes in land use (e.g. artificialization, deforestation, etc.) which affects the carbon sink potential of biomass and soils (Schmidt et al., 2015). Then, some mass balance distortions can stem from the analysis when carbon is emitted as CH₄, CO, or particulate matter (black carbon, PAH, ...) and lead to inconsistencies with GWP CH₄ calculation. This is because biogenic CH₄ oxidizes into biogenic CO₂, an effect included in the GWP characterization factor for CH₄. As a consequence, the CH₄ characterization factor is different in a 0/0 or a time biogenic carbon dioxide accounting perspective: choices need to be aligned.

In practice, the 0/0 approach is questioned for its implications in terms of interpretation of the results. First, biogenic carbon cycle flows are invisible in the contribution analysis for decision making, albeit these often represent the largest carbon flows in the bio-based sectors. Naturally, applying the 0/0 approach prevents the relevance of including time considerations in the LCA, as temporary storages of carbon in biomass would not be reflected, nor would the permanent addition of biogenic carbon to the atmosphere.

6.2. On the -1/+1 approach

This approach consists in characterizing the CO₂ LCI flows from the biosphere with a GWP or GTP characterization factor of +1 (as for fossil CO₂ flows), and to the biosphere (or Technosphere) with a

GWP characterization factor of -1. The advantages lie where the weaknesses of the 0/0 approaches stem out. The -1/+1 approach ideally accounts for all biogenic flows over the full lifecycle, with a closing carbon balance. It can also easily be adapted to include the time factor in GWP and GTP calculations. Yet, the main challenges faced by this approach can be summarized as follows.

First, the GWP or GTP scores calculated with the -1/+1 approach are sensitive to the quality of the LCI model, and particularly to carbon balance closing and completeness. There are always risks of missing the accounting of some carbon flows in the LCI analysis, regardless of the biogenic carbon LCIA accounting approach retained. For example, the precise quantification of total CO₂ uptake at biomass growth is of high relevance for the bio-based industries to seize the effects of the -1 kg CO₂-eq characterized flow. A first approximation often performed in practice consists in considering that as much carbon was captured from the atmosphere as carbon present in the product. Yet, in this case, carbon flows associated with the biomass growth but not converted into the final products (e.g. remaining in the residues, in the roots parts, or lost during biomass processing) are neglected, and similar inconsistencies can rise for multifunctional systems (e.g. if using allocation; Pawelzik et al., 2013). More comprehensive methods to capture these CO₂-uptake emissions should be implemented but currently rely on dedicated models (e.g. requiring integrated assessment modeling of agriculture production) and require consistent guidelines for example in considering baseline values for crop yields and net primary production. Naturally, GWP and GTP scores derived with the -1/+1 approach are highly sensitive to the selected system boundaries (and not only to the temporal ones) as well as models used for biogenic carbon accounting, leading to difficulties when it comes to developing comparison across studies due to their high variability (Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2023). Implementing the time approach to a cradle-to-gate LCA study could lead to carbon negative products, as emissions associated with the end-of-life would not be accounted for (Hoxha et al., 2020). Results of cradle-to-gate studies that claim net negative GWP for products are simply misleading because an important life cycle stage that contributes to GWP is purposefully omitted. On this aspect, ALIGNED recommendations are formulated in **section 7**.

6.3. On the other approaches to account for biogenic carbon flows

Other approaches emerged as alternatives to fix some of the challenges faced by the two previous methods. For example, the -1/0 approach was deemed to reestablish the promotion of bio-based products against their fossil counterparts in cradle-to-gate assessments not accounting for end-of-life emissions. In this case, applying either -1/0 or -1/+1 leads to the same GWP scores. However, the -1/0 approach presents a difference in GWP scores between cradle-to-gate and cradle-to-grave if end-of-life include emissions of non-CO₂ carbon flows (**Figure 2**).

The -1/+1* approach, also developed in the context of wood products, consists in acknowledging that landfilling and recycling can be considered as partially permanent carbon sequestration, meaning that fewer emissions should be attributed to the end-of-life of corresponding products (compared to a conventional -1/+1 approach; Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2023). This is because applying a characterization factor of +1 kg CO₂-eq per kg CO₂ regardless of the potential recycling or reuse of the product after its first life would consist in giving all the environmental (here, GWP) credits to the stakeholders implementing the potential recycling of the product. Implementing the -1/+1* approach would allow to more fairly sharing the temporary storage benefits linked to the long end-of-life (e.g. landfilling) or extended lifetime of the product (e.g. recycling) between the producer

and the waste manager or recycler. It acts as a weighting factor and was implemented to capture the benefits of temporal storage at a time when the most common end-of-life of wood products was their incineration. In practice, this methodological choice assumes a net negative biogenic carbon balance over the life cycle, acting as a credit for the estimated long-term sequestration. It also results in GWP scores being highly dependent on the end-of-life scenario, hence, is not recommended by ALIGNED.

Figure 2 – Terminology for system boundaries to develop LCA for a bio-based sector

6.4. Alignment of standards and practices

Cucurachi et al., (2022) already summarized in their Table 3 the main recommendations of existing technical standards regarding the biogenic CO₂ accounting approach to use. Most of them recommend as a first option the -1/+1 approach, such as the ISO-14067, PAS-2050, GHG Protocol, EN 167560:2015 or ILCD Handbook. Notably, they report that the PEF guideline for food/feed products prioritizes the 0/0 approach because of the short carbon cycles of edible items.

While reviewing existing LCAs of wood products, Ouellet-Plamondon et al., (2023) also noted that both the European Committee for Standardization (in the EN 15804+A2) and the Environmental Product Declaration (ISO 21930) recommend the time approach. On the other hand, they noted that the PEFCR guidelines for products with a lifetime lower than 100 years and the SIA 2032 recommended the 0/0 approach for product-level LCA data reporting.

Ouellet-Plamondon et al., (2023) also report that in France, a 0/+1 approach is used in LCA studies where wood products are incinerated as part their end-of-life, but only for cases where no trees are re-grown after wood harvesting or when this wood stemmed from native forests. They noted that the -1/+1 approach is often selected by these standards because these do require to report biogenic GWP and fossil GWP separately, or at least to separately report biogenic carbon flows at each life cycle stage (for example, ISO 14067 for carbon footprinting; (Brandão et al., 2024). Yet, debates around the right biogenic carbon accounting approach root in the larger debate of sharing the responsibilities of emissions across the different supply chains and sectors of the bio-based industry while avoiding double counting. These aspects go beyond the strict LCIA method which here should only be selected in accordance with the goal, scope and system boundaries of the LCA, cf. the ALIGNED recommendations formulated in **section 7**.

In theory, considering the full life cycle “cradle-to-grave” and disregarding temporal dynamics, the 0/0 and -1/+1 approach should lead to the same conclusions (in terms of ranking between alternatives), but the net climate change midpoint relative scores and the contribution of the different life cycle stages would weigh differently (Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2023). In practice, including time dependencies when computing climate change indicators in LCAs would be the most transparent and robust approach for the bio-based sector, but requires modelling all the GHG flows including biogenic carbon as in the -1/+1 approach (Hoxha et al., 2020).

7. Towards consistent estimation of climate impacts in LCAs of bio-based products

The following recommendations are transversal to the four challenges raised in **Section 2** and are hierarchized. First, **ensuring the consistency hence comparability of climate scores in LCAs**, not only across alternatives but also across studies and sectors, is a priority. Only then, improvements in the quality of climate change midpoint scores estimations and interpretations are unlocked and relevant. These include **improved operability of the temporal effects estimations of climate change metrics**, and **improved alignment of selected indicators with the goal of the study and the decision it is aimed at supporting**.

7.1. Baseline ALIGNED recommendations

ALIGNED proposes a set of **baseline recommendations** for consistent and comparable climate impacts scores computations in LCAs of bio-based production. In specific cases, a **degree of deviation** from these baseline recommendations is deemed tolerable, **summarized in a decision diagram** (Figure 3).

Figure 3– ALIGNED recommendations for estimating climate impacts of biobased production – synthesis.

First, ALIGNED recommends prioritizing the adoption of LCA system boundaries encompassing the full life cycle of the product system under study, that is, a **‘cradle-to-grave’ approach (Figure 2)**. If not deemed as possible in the mark of the goal and scope of the study, or simply because there is no information on the use and end-of-life of the product, **only then could a “cradle-to-gate” approach** be tolerable and applied (**Figure 3**). Further truncated systems (e.g. “gate-to-gate” approaches; **Figure 2**) are not recognized as adequate by ALIGNED to assess bio-based production, and not further addressed in this guide.

Second, ALIGNED recommends documenting and reporting separately the **biogenic from non-biogenic elementary flows** during the LCI phase. This specifically applies to carbon flows. Albeit not directly linked with the LCIA, systematically making such distinction is a prerequisite for more comprehensive and transparent climate change impact scores interpretation (see next recommendations), and also provides more flexibility to adapt the diverging standpoints of current environmental accounting standards.

Third, ALIGNED recommends documenting and assessing the climate change midpoint impacts scores with two indicators representative of two cultural perspectives: **short-term and long-term climate effects**. This recommendation is aligned with the UNEP/SETAC guidelines (Verones et al., 2020). ALIGNED recommends **GWP100** as the indicator for **short term climate effects**, because of its recognized robustness and wide use. ALIGNED recommends the **GWP500 for long term climate effects**. These are readily available in most LCA software, for example in the LCIA method IPCC (2021). More advanced climate change metrics (see **Section 4**) are computable but still require significantly more time, resources and expertise for implementation and interpretation, as notably not readily compatible with conventional LCA software.

Fourth, ALIGNED recommends implementing the -1/+1 approach for biogenic carbon dioxide flows accounting (**Section 6.2**). This is not only a prerequisite for computing time effects (next recommendation), but also deemed as essential to have comparable climate scores across studies and sectors. With the -1/+1 approach, impacts of biogenic carbon are always accounted, and ALIGNED proposes in **Figure 3** the minimum requirements for cradle-to-gate studies (not recommended) to mitigate the risks associated with the interpretation of potentially climate negative scores (side effect of the -1/+1 approach). These include always reporting climate scores of cradle-to-gate studies along with the biogenic carbon uptake used in the calculation as well as displaying separately the climate scores associated with contrasted scenarios for the use and end-of-life phases. While a biogenic-only or non-biogenic-only climate score (here, GWP or GTP) can be computed and interpreted, and **additional requirement** by ALIGNED is to always **at least providing the “total” climate score** along with the detailed interpretation and breakdown (as detailed in the ISO 14040).

Fifth, ALIGNED recommends as default to include temporal effects in the calculation of climate scores associated with biobased production. To this end, ALIGNED proposes a stepwise procedure to integrate temporal effects in practice within existing LCA studies developed with conventional LCA software. This procedure is formulated as a Tiered approach, from Tier 1 enabling a first estimation of temporal effects with limited time and resources needed to Tier 3 providing a more accurate way to account for temporal effects when computing climate change impacts (**Table 1**). A detailed tutorial is provided for each Tiered approach (*CC_tutorial_Tier1* and *CC_tutorial_Tier2-3* documents),

available in the **task repository**. These are targeted towards users with no previous experience in computing temporal effects in LCAs. Under specific conditions, obviating time effects can be tolerated (**Figure 3**) but is not recommended by ALIGNED.

Importantly, the present recommendations complement, but do not substitute applicable standards for e.g. products or carbon footprint declaration, among others.

7.2. Integrating time effects in climate scores computation in practice

On top of the baseline recommendations (previous section), **integrating time effects** in climate impacts scores **requires estimating a temporal (calendar-based) distribution of the life cycle phases**. The more refined the definition of the life cycle phases – that is LCI explicitly available for each activity, sub-activity, etc. – and the smaller the time step, the higher the accuracy. The Tiered approach should be selected according to the best available level of LCI details and temporal differentiation as well as the estimated time and resource required to implement the next Tier.

As a **minimum requirement** for sound first estimation of time effects (**Tier 1**), **at least the biomass sourcing, production, use, and end-of-life phases should be documented separately** (Figure 2). Importantly, this also applies to “cradle-to-gate” approaches (not recommended). In this case, although the use and end-of-life phases are deemed not known nor knowable (Figure 3), ALIGNED **recommends** elaborating **at least two contrasted scenarios for these phases**. The contrasted scenarios represent cases with the longer – reasonably and justified – biogenic carbon storage (e.g. use in construction sector) and alternatively cases with the shorter biogenic carbon storage (e.g. single use and incineration). All calculations, assumptions, etc. used to estimate the temporal distribution and elaborate the use and end-of-life scenarios should be documented.

Once the temporal distribution of the LCI is performed, ALIGNED provides a tool for computing GWP100 and GWP500 scores as well as GMTC and iGMTC results as a function of the temporal distribution of three main GHGs: CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O. The tool not only provides an updated and updatable version of time-explicit characterization factors for all indicators, but also directly estimates the total climate scores – for each indicator – related to a given time-explicit inventory². The tutorials further describe how to use the tool depending on the selected Tier (**Table 1**).

² Other GHGs such as HFCs and SF₆ are omitted because typically not specific to biobased production. Seasoned practitioners are invited to extend ALIGNED tools to these gases – and share their enhancements to the community.

Table 1 ALIGNED Tiered approach for including time effects in climate change scores computation

Tutorials:	Tiers 1	Tiers 2	Tiers 3
GHGs covered	CO ₂ , CH ₄ and N ₂ O	CO ₂ , CH ₄ and N ₂ O	CO ₂ , CH ₄ and N ₂ O
Time step	Representative durations for at least four main stages: Biomass sourcing, Production, Use and End-of-life	Foreground LCI flows defined yearly over the full life cycle duration	Foreground LCI flows defined yearly over the full life cycle duration
Ease of implementation	Roughly define temporality of each life cycle stage. Set GHG inventories for all life cycle stages	Define temporal distribution of GHG flows on a yearly basis	Automatically done with Tier 2.
Climate midpoint indicators included	GWP100 and GWP500	GWP100 and GWP500	GMTC and iGMTC functions
Ease of interpretation	Check whether temporality is critical in the studied system	Temporal effects are disaggregated, contribution of each life cycle stage can be identified	Discussions on a wider set of indicators enabled

Again, the proposed Tiered approach is deemed to facilitate the inclusion of time effects in climate change impact calculations for users and practitioners not familiar with dynamic LCAs. If already familiar with such approaches, then ALIGNED recommends using the best methods available (expert level; see **Section 5.3**). Here, not all GHGs were temporalized, nor background system emissions, which is a limit to acknowledge when interpreting the results. The proposed approach is nevertheless a step forward as most LCA studies still do not include time considerations, as they are not easily implementable within conventional LCA software: a solution is provided here.

8. Conclusion

This document delivered a synthesis of the main challenges in estimating the climate change impacts of bio-based production, provided an overview of existing solutions and methods, and finally improved substantially their usability and implementation for LCA practitioners. Grounded on an extended review of the theoretical background of existing climate change assessment frameworks tailored to LCA, a baseline set of recommendations towards consistent and transparent estimation of climate impacts in LCAs of bio-based production was formulated (**Figure 3**). The practical inclusion of temporal effects on climate impacts scores within conventional LCA software was unlocked. To this end, ALIGNED developed a time-explicit characterization factors estimation tool and formulated stepwise tutorials, available in the ALIGNED **data repository**.

9. References

- Andersen, C.E., Rasmussen, F.N., Habert, G., Birgisdóttir, H., 2021. Embodied GHG Emissions of Wooden Buildings—Challenges of Biogenic Carbon Accounting in Current LCA Methods. *Front. Built Environ.* 7.
- Beloin-Saint-Pierre, D., Albers, A., Hélias, A., Tiruta-Barna, L., Fantke, P., Levasseur, A., Benetto, E., Benoist, A., Collet, P., 2020. Addressing temporal considerations in life cycle assessment. *Science of The Total Environment* 743, 140700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.140700>
- Brandão, M., Kirschbaum, M.U.F., Cowie, A.L., 2024. Evaluating metrics for quantifying the climate-change effects of land-based carbon fluxes. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 29, 328–343. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-023-02251-0>
- Breton, C., Blanchet, P., Amor, B., Beauregard, R., Chang, W.-S., 2018. Assessing the Climate Change Impacts of Biogenic Carbon in Buildings: A Critical Review of Two Main Dynamic Approaches. *Sustainability* 10, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10062020>
- Bulle, C., Margni, M., Patouillard, L., Boulay, A.-M., Bourgault, G., De Bruille, V., Cao, V., Hauschild, M., Henderson, A., Humbert, S., Kashef-Haghighi, S., Kounina, A., Laurent, A., Levasseur, A., Liard, G., Rosenbaum, R.K., Roy, P.-O., Shaked, S., Fantke, P., Jolliet, O., 2019. IMPACT World+: a globally regionalized life cycle impact assessment method. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 24, 1653–1674. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-019-01583-0>
- Cain, M., Lynch, J., Allen, M.R., Fuglestedt, J.S., Frame, D.J., Macey, A.H., 2019. Improved calculation of warming-equivalent emissions for short-lived climate pollutants. *npj Clim Atmos Sci* 2, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-019-0086-4>
- Calvin, K., Dasgupta, D., Krinner, G., Mukherji, A., Thorne, P.W., Trisos, C., Romero, J., Aldunce, P., Barrett, K., Blanco, G., Cheung, W.W.L., Connors, S., Denton, F., Diongue-Niang, A., Dodman, D., Garschagen, M., Geden, O., Hayward, B., Jones, C., Jotzo, F., Krug, T., Lasco, R., Lee, Y.-Y., Masson-Delmotte, V., Meinshausen, M., Mintenbeck, K., Mokssit, A., Otto, F.E.L., Pathak, M., Pirani, A., Poloczanska, E., Pörtner, H.-O., Revi, A., Roberts, D.C., Roy, J., Ruane, A.C., Skea, J., Shukla, P.R., Slade, R., Slangen, A., Sokona, Y., Sörensson, A.A., Tignor, M., Van Vuuren, D., Wei, Y.-M., Winkler, H., Zhai, P., Zommers, Z., Hourcade, J.-C., Johnson, F.X., Pachauri, S., Simpson, N.P., Singh, C., Thomas, A., Totin, E., Arias, P., Bustamante, M., Elgizouli, I., Flato, G., Howden, M., Méndez-Vallejo, C., Pereira, J.J., Pichs-Madruga, R., Rose, S.K., Saheb, Y., Sánchez Rodríguez, R., Ürge-Vorsatz, D., Xiao, C., Yassaa, N., Alegría, A., Armour, K., Bednar-Friedl, B., Blok, K., Cissé, G., Dentener, F., Eriksen, S., Fischer, E., Garner, G., Guivarch, C., Haasnoot, M., Hansen, G., Hauser, M., Hawkins, E., Hermans, T., Kopp, R., Leprince-Ringuet, N., Lewis, J., Ley, D., Ludden, C., Niamir, L., Nicholls, Z., Some, S., Szopa, S., Trewin, B., Van Der Wijst, K.-I., Winter, G., Witting, M., Birt, A., Ha, M., Romero, J., Kim, J., Haites, E.F., Jung, Y., Stavins, R., Birt, A., Ha, M., Orendain, D.J.A., Ignon, L., Park, S., Park, Y., Reisinger, A., Cammaramo, D., Fischlin, A., Fuglestedt, J.S., Hansen, G., Ludden, C., Masson-Delmotte, V., Matthews, J.B.R., Mintenbeck, K., Pirani, A., Poloczanska, E., Leprince-Ringuet, N., Péan, C., 2023. Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Core Writing Team, H. Lee and J. Romero (eds.)]. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), Geneva, Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.59327/IPCC/AR6-9789291691647>
- Cherubini, F., Peters, G.P., Berntsen, T., Strømman, A.H., Hertwich, E., 2011. CO₂ emissions from biomass combustion for bioenergy: atmospheric decay and contribution to global warming. *GCB Bioenergy* 3, 413–426. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1757-1707.2011.01102.x>

- Cucurachi, S., Steubing, B., Siebler, F., Navarre, N., Caldeira, C., Sala, S., 2022. Prospective LCA methodology for novel and emerging technologies for bio-based products : the Planet Bio project. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Durão, V., Silvestre, J.D., Mateus, R., de Brito, J., 2020. Assessment and communication of the environmental performance of construction products in Europe: Comparison between PEF and EN 15804 compliant EPD schemes. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 156, 104703. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104703>
- Frischknecht, R., Fantke, P., Tschümperlin, L., Niero, M., Antón, A., Bare, J., Boulay, A.-M., Cherubini, F., Hauschild, M.Z., Henderson, A., Levasseur, A., McKone, T.E., Michelsen, O., I Canals, L.M., Pfister, S., Ridoutt, B., Rosenbaum, R.K., Verones, F., Vigon, B., Jolliet, O., 2016. Global guidance on environmental life cycle impact assessment indicators: progress and case study. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 21, 429–442. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-015-1025-1>
- Hoxha, E., Passer, A., Saade, M.R.M., Trigaux, D., Shuttleworth, A., Pittau, F., Allacker, K., Habert, G., 2020. Biogenic carbon in buildings: a critical overview of LCA methods 1, 504–524. <https://doi.org/10.5334/bc.46>
- Inman, M., 2008. Carbon is forever. *Nature Climate Change* 1, 156–158. <https://doi.org/10.1038/climate.2008.122>
- Iordan, C.-M., Kuipers, K.J.J., Huang, B., Hu, X., Verones, F., Cherubini, F., 2023. Spatially and taxonomically explicit characterisation factors for greenhouse gas emission impacts on biodiversity. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 198, 107159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107159>
- IPCC, 2021. *Climate Change 2021 – The Physical Science Basis: Working Group I Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, 1st ed. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896>
- ISO, 2006. *Environmental management: life cycle assessment; Principles and Framework*.
- Levasseur, A., Lesage, P., Margni, M., Deschênes, L., Samson, R., 2010. Considering Time in LCA: Dynamic LCA and Its Application to Global Warming Impact Assessments. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 44, 3169–3174. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es9030003>
- Lynch, J., Cain, M., Pierrehumbert, R., Allen, M., 2020. Demonstrating GWP*: a means of reporting warming-equivalent emissions that captures the contrasting impacts of short- and long-lived climate pollutants. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 15, 044023. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab6d7e>
- Meinshausen, M., Nicholls, Z., 2022. GWP* is a model, not a metric. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 17, 041002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac5930>
- Negishi, K., Tiruta-Barna, L., Schiopu, N., Lebert, A., Chevalier, J., 2018. An operational methodology for applying dynamic Life Cycle Assessment to buildings. *Build Environ.* 144, 611–621. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2018.09.005>
- Olivié, D.J.L., Peters, G.P., 2013. Variation in emission metrics due to variation in CO₂ and temperature impulse response functions. *Earth System Dynamics* 4, 267–286. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-4-267-2013>
- Ouellet-Plamondon, C.M., Ramseier, L., Balouktsi, M., Delem, L., Foliente, G., Francart, N., Garcia-Martinez, A., Hoxha, E., Lützkendorf, T., Nygaard Rasmussen, F., Peupartier, B., Butler, J., Birgisdottir, H., Dowdell, D., Dixit, M.K., Gomes, V., Gomes da Silva, M., Gómez de Cózar, J.C., Kjendseth Wiik, M., Llatas, C., Mateus, R., Pulgrossi, L.M., Röck, M., Saade, M.R.M., Passer, A., Satola, D., Seo, S., Soust Verdaguer, B., Veselka, J., Volf, M., Zhang, X., Frischknecht, R., 2023. Carbon footprint assessment of a wood multi-residential building considering biogenic carbon. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 404, 136834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136834>

- Pawelzik, P., Carus, M., Hotchkiss, J., Narayan, R., Selke, S., Wellisch, M., Weiss, M., Wicke, B., Patel, M.K., 2013. Critical aspects in the life cycle assessment (LCA) of bio-based materials – Reviewing methodologies and deriving recommendations. *Resour. Conserv. Recy.* 73, 211–228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2013.02.006>
- Rosenbaum, R.K., 2018. Overview of Existing LCIA Methods—Annex to Chapter 10, in: Hauschild, M.Z., Rosenbaum, R.K., Olsen, S.I. (Eds.), *Life Cycle Assessment*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 1147–1183. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56475-3_40
- Schmidt, J.H., Weidema, B.P., Brandão, M., 2015. A framework for modelling indirect land use changes in Life Cycle Assessment. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 99, 230–238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.03.013>
- Sevigné-Itoiz, E., Mwabonje, O., Panoutsou, C., Woods, J., 2021. Life cycle assessment (LCA): informing the development of a sustainable circular bioeconomy? *Philos. Trans. Royal Soc. A* 379, 20200352. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0352>
- Shen, Z., Tiruta-Barna, L., Hamelin, L., 2022. From hemp grown on carbon-vulnerable lands to long-lasting bio-based products: Uncovering trade-offs between overall environmental impacts, sequestration in soil, and dynamic influences on global temperature. *Sci. Total Environ.* 846, 157331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157331>
- Shimako, A.H., Tiruta-Barna, L., Bisinella de Faria, A.B., Ahmadi, A., Spérandio, M., 2018. Sensitivity analysis of temporal parameters in a dynamic LCA framework. *Sci. Total Environ.* 624, 1250–1262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.220>
- Shimako, A.H., Tiruta-Barna, L., Pigné, Y., Benetto, E., Navarrete Gutiérrez, T., Guiraud, P., Ahmadi, A., 2016a. Environmental assessment of bioenergy production from microalgae based systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 139, 51–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.08.003>
- Shimako, A.H., Tiruta-Barna, L., Pigné, Y., Benetto, E., Navarrete Gutiérrez, T., Guiraud, P., Ahmadi, A., 2016b. Environmental assessment of bioenergy production from microalgae based systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 139, 51–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.08.003>
- Shine, K.P., Fuglestvedt, J.S., Hailemariam, K., Stuber, N., 2005. Alternatives to the Global Warming Potential for Comparing Climate Impacts of Emissions of Greenhouse Gases. *Climatic Change* 68, 281–302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-005-1146-9>
- Smith, M.A., Cain, M., Allen, M.R., 2021. Further improvement of warming-equivalent emissions calculation. *npj Clim Atmos Sci* 4, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-021-00169-8>
- Tiruta-Barna, L., 2021. A climate goal-based, multicriteria method for system evaluation in life cycle assessment. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 26, 1913–1931. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-021-01991-1>
- Ventura, A., 2022. Conceptual issue of the dynamic GWP indicator and solution. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 28, 788–799. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-022-02028-x>
- Verones, F., Hellweg, S., Antón, A., Azevedo, L.B., Chaudhary, A., Cosme, N., Cucurachi, S., de Baan, L., Dong, Y., Fantke, P., Golsteijn, L., Hauschild, M., Heijungs, R., Joliet, O., Juraske, R., Larsen, H., Laurent, A., Mutel, C.L., Margni, M., Núñez, M., Owsianiak, M., Pfister, S., Ponsioen, T., Preiss, P., Rosenbaum, R.K., Roy, P.-O., Sala, S., Steinmann, Z., van Zelm, R., Van Dingenen, R., Vieira, M., Huijbregts, M.A.J., 2020. LC-IMPACT: A regionalized life cycle damage assessment method. *Journal of Industrial Ecology* 24, 1201–1219. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13018>
- Zuiderveen, E.A.R., Kuipers, K.J.J., Caldeira, C., Hanssen, S.V., van der Hulst, M.K., de Jonge, M.M.J., Vlysidis, A., van Zelm, R., Sala, S., Huijbregts, M.A.J., 2023. The potential of emerging bio-based products to reduce environmental impacts. *Nat Commun* 14, 8521. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-43797-9>